

SIDEA – Società Italiana di Economia Agraria
LIX Convegno annuale

Agricoltura, alimentazione e mondo rurale di fronte ai cambiamenti dello scenario globale: politiche e strategie per la sostenibilità e la resilienza

Marina di Orosei (NU), 21– 22 settembre 2023

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

The role of upstream actors in the management of fresh fruit & vegetables surplus and losses

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PAROLE CHIAVE

Fruit and vegetables, food losses, prevention, innovation, Q methodology, Producers' Organization

1 INTRODUCTION

The fruit and vegetable (F&V) value chain is essential for the global food system. Yet F&V wastage still occurs along the value chain despite their necessity for a healthy diet (FAO,2019). Prevention and reduction of food losses and waste (FLW) in the agrifood sector is one of the main challenges of recent years to avoid the wastage of resources and nutritious products. According to FAO (2019,2021), the term “food losses” is referred to the reduction in edible food mass during the upstream phases of the agrifood value chain (production, post-harvest, and processing phase) while “food waste” is the discarding of edible food at retail and consumer levels. Food losses is an economic issue for the all the actor of the F&V value chain, with special implication for farmers. In Europe, to strengthen farmers’ collective bargaining power and support their investments they can organize their business to participate in Producer organisations (POs) or associations of producer organisations (APOs). This allows farmers to concentrate the supply and improve their marketing powers. Farmers, POs and AOPs, together with broker and expert can be considered the main actors during the upstream phases of the agrifood value chain. In the EU, the OCM regime supports POs for implementing Operational Programmes with funding contributions (Reg. 1308/2013). The operational program has a duration of 3 to 5 years, each year a PO or AOP may set up an Operational Fund to finance the investments included in the operational programme. The operational fund is financed jointly by the financial contribution of members (or the PO itself) and the EU financial assistance. It is possible to finance different types of measure through Operation Fund, yet investments in measure to reduce food surplus and losses is still residual compared with other types of investments (OERSA,2020). The choice about the type of investments to be included in the operational program is made jointly between the farmers

and the PO's corporate structure (European Commission, 2013). This joint decision-making process ensures that the investments align with the interests and needs of all parties. Nonetheless, the actors in the F&V value chain have different expertise and backgrounds, and this may hamper their knowledge on the topic of food losses prevention. In general, there may be a willingness to address FLW but, from a business perspective, wasting food might be rationale without a supportive framework and a positive trade-off between the cost of introducing an innovation and the expected impact (Tort *et al.*, 2021). Cooperation, also defined as 'co-innovation', among actors is reported to be an element of success for innovation in the food industry, but there are only a few studies in the literature on the perception of innovations along the F&V value chain, compared to the existing literature on assessing consumers opinions of new food and technologies (Tort *et al.*, 2012; Mandolesi *et al.*, 2015). This is one of the first study on the perception of a sample of upstream actors on the F&V value chain towards innovation to prevent food losses and improve the management of surplus products. The purpose of this study is to contribute to the narrative of sustainable F&V value chain and to extrapolate indication about which strategies and related innovative operations management, if pursued with a shared preference, would have greater success and adhesion among operators. A Q methodology framework is set to collect, assess, and discuss the similarities in the viewpoint of the actors and to report their opinion towards innovative practices that shall enhance their operation's sustainability.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The prevention of food waste in the F&V supply chain is a pressing challenge with significant economic and environmental implications. In this study, we propose a multidimensional theoretical framework that integrates key concepts starting from Rogers' Innovation Adoption Theory (Rogers, 1962), Value Chain Management Theory by Porter (Porter, 1985) and The Circular Economy theory. Rogers' seminal work on the diffusion of innovations offers valuable insights into how individuals or organizations adopt new ideas or practices. In the context of this study, stakeholders' preferences are considered to influence their assessment of the relative advantage of innovative solutions within operational program, perceived compatibility with existing practices, complexity, and observability. Understanding stakeholders' perspectives on these attributes will guide the design of investment plans and encourage the adoption of sustainable practices (Rogers, 1962; Van Huylenbroeck *et al.*, 2018). The concept of value chain management emphasizes the importance of collaboration and coordination among supply chain actors to reduce waste and maximize value creation. Stakeholders' preferences are critical in identifying investment opportunities and developing operational program that align with the principles of sustainable F&V value chain. Coordinated efforts along the supply chain can enable the implementation of circular practices, such as waste reduction initiatives and the adoption of resource-efficient technologies (Porter, 1985; Beamon *et al.*, 1998). The circular economy approach focuses on minimizing waste generation, promoting resource reuse, and closing material loops. Stakeholders' preferences towards specific circular economy practices, such as investments in sustainable packaging, waste valorisation, and recycling technologies, will be pivotal in designing operational program that drive the transition towards circular practices in the F&V value chain (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2015; Geng *et al.*, 2019). The exploration of stakeholders' preferences is made using the Q methodology, which provides a unique approach to capturing individual perspectives within a complex decision-making context (Stephenson, 1935; Brown, 1980). By combining insights from relevant economic theories about the adoption and diffusion of innovations with material collected from interviews with experts, the aim of this research is to gain a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing stakeholders' preferences and willingness to invest in sustainable practices through operational programmes.

3 METHODOLOGY

This work was conducted as part of the H2020 project [omitted for review]. One of the institutional partners involved in the project had a key role in improving the recruitment of a sample of experts and organizations to be interviewed by offering information collected on digital platform provided in the project. The methodology adopted for this study was developed in the 1930s by W. Stephenson to shift from variable factor analysis, R methodology, to person factor analysis, Q methodology. The Q methodology allows to use information collected from subjects to identify common and/or divergent patterns on a given topic. During the data collection process, each subject is invited to explain their personal preferences in their own words, allowing the possibility of identifying relationships by interpreting the subject's point of view (Mandolesi *et al.*, 2015). Q methodology implementation consists of five steps: construction of the concourse, development of the Q sample, selection of the P set, Q sorting, and Q factor analysis. The concourse refers to "the flow of communicability surrounding any topic" (Brown, 1993): a collection of all the statements about the topic of the study. In this research, the narrative around innovations to improve the management of surplus and prevent food losses in the fresh F&V value chain was developed by combining scientific research, grey literature, direct interviews with supply chain experts, consultant and researcher involved in [omitted for review] project. More than 300 statements were collected and analysed. A deductive factorial design was employed to classify all viable assertions into theoretical categories and then organized into a 9-cell matrix (3x3) to reduce the amount to a representative yet manageable set of statements (Table 1). For the aim of this study, the theoretical class "Type of innovation" includes three approaches to innovations, as described by the Oslo Manual (OECD,2018). The "Scope of the actions" category is derived by the "Waste hierarchy framework" in the F&V sector (WRAP, 201). The final Q sample is composed of 34 statements to represent the concourse.

Table 1 – Sampling Matrix

	Q sample (n = 34 statements)	Type of innovation		
		Technological & Product Innovation	Organizational Innovation	Marketing Innovation
Scope of the actions	Prevention of food losses	4	4	4
	Optimization of F&V products	4	4	4
	Food losses recycling and recovery	3	4	3

After a pilot test, the Q sample was refined, and the statements were reorganized to include all the possible feedback. As suggested by Webeler & Danielson (2009), the P set (participant sample) was structured to include subjects with knowledge and/or roles coherent with the topic who are invited to freely express their opinion (Table 2). POs (also representing farmers point of view), APOs, and supply chain experts (e.g., agronomists, innovation brokers, and intermediaries) are part of the final sample. The participant in the sample were randomly chosen to assure the representativeness of different points of view. As reported in Table 2, the P sample is composed by 14 participants of which 42% is women. Most of the participant have more than 10 years of experience in the sector, and different role in the innovation process: adopter (those directly involved in the decision about the adoption of an innovation), non-adopter, and innovation broker (Clark *et al.*, 2002; Winch *et al.*, 2007).

Table 2 - P Sample

Q-sort ID	Value chain level	Main occupation	Gender	Age	Experience in the sector	Role in the innovation
1	AOP	Association Service Manager	F	40-45	> 15 years	Adopter
2	AOP	Operational Plans Manager	M	50-55	> 10 years	Adopter
3	OP	Operational Plans Manager	M	60-65	> 20 years	Adopter
4	OP	Association Service Manager	F	40-45	>10 years	Adopter
5	OP	OCM manager	F	40-45	>10 years	Adopter
6	OP	Market Withdrawals Manager	F	35-40	> 5 years	Adopter
7	OP	CEO	M	60-65	> 20 years	Adopter
8	Entrepreneurs	Buyer	M	45-50	> 15 years	Non-adopter
9	Research sector	Expert	M	30-35	> 5 years	Innovation broker
10	Research sector	Agronomist	F	30-35	> 5 years	Non-adopter
11	Research sector	Expert	F	40-45	> 15 years	Innovation broker
12	Research sector	Agronomist	M	40-45	> 15 years	Innovation broker
13	Entrepreneurs	Expert	M	35-40	> 5 years	Adopter
14	Entrepreneurs	Buyer	M	40-45	>15 years	Innovation broker

The *Q sorting* process consists of data collection organized by one-to-one remote interviews. The online tool Miro (<https://miro.com/it/>) was used to present the statements in the form of digital cards and to sort each one on the *Q sorting* grid (Table 3).

Table 3 - Q sorting grid

Mostly Disagree				Neutral				Mostly Agree
+1	+2	+3	+4	+5	+6	+7	+8	+9
+1	+2	+3	+4	+5	+6	+7	+8	+9
	+2	+3	+4	+5	+6	+7	+8	
		+3	+4	+5	+6	+7		
			+4	+5	+6			
				+5				

Firstly, the interviewees were asked to read the cards and divide the statements into 3 groups: the statements with which they most agree, the statements with which they don't agree, and the statements with which they feel neutral. Then they were asked to sort the 34 statements, following the sorting condition: "For each statement, indicate, based on your preferences, if you agree, disagree, or are neutral to the effectiveness of the practice or innovation for the management of production surpluses and preventing food losses", from the "most like" (+9) to the "least like" (+1), starting from the extremes, "forcing" a normal distribution. During and after the Q sorting process, the participants were invited to explain their point of view and express their subjectivity. The analysis of the Q sorts was conducted using the Kade Q software. The Q sorts were analysed using a Principal Component Analysis, adopting a varimax rotation analysis to maximize the amount of study variance explained (Watts and Stenner, 2012). Following a scree plot test on the eigenvalues, three factors have been chosen to be analysed, representing 61% of the explained variance. The factors are the individualized opinions that result from the Q sorting process, so each factor represents a subjective point of view shared by the participants with a similar Q sorting. Then, a factor estimation based on factor loading value is made to perform the varimax rotation. Each Q-sort is related to each factor and as suggested by Brown, the number of Q-sorts to be rotated was based on the value of the factor loading (correlation between Q sorts) that were statistically significant at the 0.05 level ($\pm 1.96 \times 1/\sqrt{n}$, of statements, e.g., ± 0.34). As showed in Table 4, those Q-sorts that present a statistically significant factor loadings are selected to be rotated. This technique is used to extract from each factor the objective point of view expressed by the Q sort.

Table 4 - Factor loadings

N. Q-sort ID	Q-sort	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3
8	Exp	0.9214*	0.1415	-0.0753
14	Exp	0.9105*	0.0878	-0.0907
9	Exp	0.8964*	0.0351	0.1281
5	OP	0.5409*	0.0742	0.3653
3	AOP	0.1089	0.9382*	0.1175
2	OP	0.1100	0.9217*	0.1135
4	AOP	-0.0576	0.6136*	0.0109
1	OP	0.2328	0.4424*	-0.0132

7	OP	0.2594	0.4081*	0.0711
6	OP	-0.1562	0.3515*	0.1918
12	Exp	-0.1515	0.0949	0.8879*
11	Exp	0.1873	0.0992	0.8068*
10	Exp	-0.162	0.3917	0.7053*
13	Exp	0.3611	-0.0907	0.6136*
	N. of defining variables	4	6	4
	% explained variance	28	19	14
	Cumulative % explained variance	28	47	61

Each factor is characterized by distinguish and consensus statements (those sorted in similar position by the participants in the factor) that gives an indication about the shared attitudes, or points of view, on the debate surrounding the subject under study and allows the study of the discourse (subjective point of view shared by the participant in a factor). To represent graphically the positions represented by the three-discourse extracted from the sample a Discourse positioning diagram is showed in the next paragraph (Table 5).

4 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The interpretation of factors proceeded in terms of factor arrays. Each extracted factor represents a different point of view on the topic of the study, and it is shared by those Q sorts that sorted a statement in the same position (Figure 4).

Factor 1 – Valorisation of F&V losses

This factor high ranked the efficacy of valorisation innovations as a solution to improve the management of food losses. In their opinion coordinated actions of all the actor in the value chain to promote the recovery of food losses is the key for a step towards more circularity in the sector. Furthermore, they call for more experts in the field of circular economy to find valuable path to prevent and valorise food losses. On the contrary, they low ranked the possibility to negotiate new type of contract with the retailer in the case of adoption of strategies to reduce food losses and waste. They main reason for this is that they “do not believe that is feasible to negotiate such type of contracts” because of their low market power.

Factor 2 – Optimization of surplus management

Factor 2 point of view is focused on the management of surplus products and promotion of prevention actions. The distinguish statements of this factor are related to innovations which focuses on the redistribution of surplus food and the participation in digital platform to enhance the use of funds and innovations. On the contrary, this factor low ranked innovation at farmer level to produce energy from food losses. This factor showed high agreement towards the role of innovation to promote the quality of food products.

Factor 3 – Focus on sustainability actions

This factor is composed only by the Q-sorts of experts. Factor 3 is composed only by the Q-sorts of experts. They high ranked those statements which emphasize new market approaches to optimize the surplus of product and to prevent food losses. The point of view of this factor aligns with sustainability actions, reflecting the academic expertise of the experts and the commitment for the development of sustainable practices.

Discourse positioning diagram

The factor analysis reveals three distinct viewpoints within the context of food loss prevention and surplus management innovations. Factor 1 focus on the importance of valorisation actions, Factor 2 emphasizes the improvement of surplus management and prevention strategies, and Factor 3 centres on sustainability actions. These results underscore the heterogeneity of viewpoints among stakeholders within the F&V value chain. According to the framework developed for this Q methodological study a Discourse positioning diagram was created to assess graphically each factor in respect of the category of innovation underneath (Table 5)

Table 5 - Discourse positioning diagram

The graphical analysis of the discourses shows us different approaches towards the prevention of F&V losses. While Factor 1 is more oriented towards the improvement of the recovery chain, giving an added value to by-products and waste, Factor 2 and Factor 3 viewpoints on innovations are more focused on prevention and optimization action by the development of new market channel and cooperative business model.

5 CONCLUSION

Funds to improve the efficiency and sustainability of the operations are ready and available through European and national funding programs, but the intensity of research and development within the agrifood sector is reported to be still relatively low compared to other key sectors (European Commission, 2022). At the same time, the European policy framework asked for actions to prevent the volume of FLW generated from improving food security and granting an income to farmers. Although the findings of any Q study cannot be generalized to the population because they are only specific to the participants, the various and relevant points of view included in the current study offer a valid representation of the potential range of the main relevant perspectives in the general population. The point of view emerged from the factors can be a reference for future policies to move towards collaborative value chain processes and participatory research methods, which will also make it easier to embrace innovations and serve as a springboard for new regulations (Iofrida *et al.*, 2018). The main key message emerged from this study is that the efficient management of food products is affected by different factors and collaborative strategies using digital tools

together with the introduction of expert in circular economy. At the same time, valorisation practice shall be considered and improved to gain an added value also from the fraction of food losses that is still unavoidable. The shared insights bear significant implications for policy development, as they provide a deeper understanding of stakeholders' preferences and priorities. Also, this research can contribute to the identification of drivers for change and valuable opportunities for innovations to be introduced into the F&V sector. Indeed, promoting policies and actions which do not encounter the agreement of the actors who are in charge to implement them is not efficient nor it can finally exert a real impact on FLW reduction.

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